

Interactions of thiourea and L-cysteine with $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ {tap = 2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine} in aqueous medium : Kinetic and mechanistic studies

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Abstract : The kinetics of the interactions of thiourea and L-cysteine with the title complex were studied spectrophotometrically as a function of complex and ligand concentrations, pH and temperature at constant ionic strength. The substitution reactions show two consecutive steps : the first is the ligand-assisted anation followed by a chelation step. The activation parameters for both the steps have been evaluated using Eyring equation. The low positive value of ΔH^\ddagger and the large negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicate an associative mode of activation for both the aqua ligand substitution processes. The products of the reactions have been characterized with the help of infrared and electrospray ionization mass spectroscopic analysis.

Keywords : Kinetics, interaction, $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$, thiourea, L-cysteine.

Introduction

All chemotherapeutic drugs have drawbacks, including intrinsic or acquired resistance, toxicity, and consequent side effects. Cis-platin^{1,2} is no exception. The anti-cancer drug cis-platin, or cis-DDP is well known but its toxicity has led to the search for second and third generation drugs with the same therapeutic activity comparable to that of cis-platin but with reduced toxicity³. Efforts to mitigate the drawbacks have prompted chemists to synthesise a variety of analogues, but only a handful of new drugs have resulted that have been shown to be suitable for clinical application. Improved understanding of the mechanism of action of cis-platin, resulting from the efforts of many research groups during the last three decades, has rationalised the design of new platinum drugs, and drugs based on other metals such as ruthenium. This overview will begin with a brief introduction to the molecular, kinetic and thermodynamic details of the coordination chemistry of medicinally relevant metals, focusing on platinum, ruthenium and other noble metals that have been shown to possess important biological properties. Now it is established that among the metal complexes ruthenium complexes have considerable antibacterial

power like other platinum, rhodium and palladium complexes^{4,5}. Work with nucleosides and nucleic acids indicate that the coordination of ruthenium(II) to such ligands is similar to that of cis-platin or its analogues. Ruthenium complexes are an order of magnitude less toxic than cis-platin^{6,7}. Trans-[Cl₄(Me₂SO)(Im)Ru^{III}]⁻ (Im = imidazole) is the first ruthenium compound that successfully entered phase I clinical trial⁸. The studies on the bioactivity of ruthenium(II/III) complexes are still a developing area. However the metal sulphur compounds such as thioethers could perhaps serve as a drug reservoir for metal ion at DNA⁹.

Thiourea and L-cysteine are sulphur containing ligands. Flexidentate property as well as ability to bind as neutral, monoanions or dianions makes thiourea a versatile ligand. Both the free thiourea and their metal complexes display a wide range of biological activity, including antibacterial, antifungal, antitubercular, antithyroid, antihelminthic, rodenticidal, insecticidal, herbicidal and plant-growth regulator properties¹⁰⁻¹⁴. L-Cysteine, a nonessential amino acid, is marketed in nutritional supplements as an antioxidant, immune system booster and has been reported to improve muscle recovery following vigorous exercise and

soft tissue recovery following injury or surgery.

In view of the above, in the present article we present mechanistic aspects of the interactions of thiourea and L-cysteine with the title complex in aqueous medium, where ruthenium(II) is stable even at biological pH 7.4 due to the presence of an excellent π -acceptor ligand, tap{2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine}¹⁵.

Experimental

Materials :

The compound *cis*-diaqua-bis-{2-(*m*-tolylazo) pyridine} ruthenium(II) diperchlorate, monohydrate, *cis*-[Ru(tap)₂(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂.H₂O was prepared following the literature method^{16,17}, and the reacting complex ion [(H₂O)(tap)₂RuORu(tap)₂(H₂O)]²⁺ (**1**) was prepared *in situ* at pH 7.4. The reaction products of thiourea (**2**) and L-cysteine (**3**) with complex **1** were prepared by mixing the reactants in 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 5, and 1 : 10 ratios and thermostated at 50 °C for 72 h. The electronic spectra of **2**, **3** (Fig. 1) show complete complexation between the complex **1** with the two ligands thiourea and L-cysteine.

Product analysis :

The composition of the products were determined by Job's method of continuous variation, which indicated a 2 : 1 metal to ligand ratio for all two products (**2**, **3**) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Spectra of complex **1**, thiourea substituted complex **2**, L-cysteine substituted complex **3**. [Complex **1**] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [ligands] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH = 7.4.

Fig. 2. Job's plot for the reaction of complex **1** with thiourea.

When complex **1** and thiourea was mixed in 2 : 1 molar ratio at pH 7.4, a violet product (**2**) was obtained. The IR spectrum of free thiourea displays two sharp bands at 3402 and 3295 cm⁻¹, assignable to asymmetric and symmetric -NH₂ group modes respectively. These remain at almost the same positions in the product complex (**2**), suggesting that the amino group is not involved in coordination. The IR spectrum of product complex, in KBr disc shows prominent bands at 1114 cm⁻¹. The C=S stretching frequency of the free thiourea occurs at 1206 cm⁻¹ which is shifted 92 cm⁻¹ downwards to 1114 cm⁻¹ indicating the coordination of the C=S group of thiourea to Ru²⁺ through the S atom. The spectrum suggests that the final product is a S coordinated chelate and thiourea acts as a bridging ligand.

When complex **1** and L-cysteine was mixed in 2 : 1 molar ratio at pH 7.4, here also a violet product (**3**) was obtained. The IR spectrum of product, in KBr disc shows strong bands at the region 3000–3380 cm⁻¹ together with medium bands at 1570 cm⁻¹. The asymmetric COO⁻ stretching frequency (ν_{asym}) of the free ligand (L-cysteine) occurs at 1575 cm⁻¹ which remains in almost same position (1568 cm⁻¹) in the product complex indicating that the COO⁻ group of L-cysteine is not involved in bonding with metal. The asymmetric COO⁻ stretching frequency (ν_{asym}) of the acid occurs at 1580–1660 cm⁻¹, when the group is coordinated to metal, whereas a non coordinated COO⁻ group has the $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ stretching

at lower frequencies¹⁸. The IR spectrum of free ligand (L-cysteine) displays a sharp peak near $\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to free -SH group but there is no peak at near $\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stretching frequency of free -SH group) in the final product complex. This fact indicates that bonding occurred through S atom of L-cysteine. The band at $3000\text{--}3380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to an NH stretching frequency which is also observed in the IR spectrum of the free ligand. The spectrum suggests that bonding not occurred through the carboxyl group or amino group but bonding occurred through S atom of L-cysteine.

From ESI-mass spectra of both the two products have been characterized which has been shown in supplementary part (Figs. S1 to S4).

Measurements :

The pH of the solution was adjusted with $\text{HClO}_4/\text{NaOH}$ and measured with a Sartorius pH meter (Model PB11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 . Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength ($0.1\text{ mol dm}^{-3}\text{ NaClO}_4$).

IR spectra (KBr disc, $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were measured using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR Model RX1 infrared spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a micromass Q-ToF microTM mass spectrometer (Micromass, EquipNet, Inc., Canton, MA) in +ve ion mode.

All the spectral and kinetic measurements were done using a Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-1601 PC), attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (Model TCC-240A with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

For L-cysteine the progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 560 nm , and for thiourea the progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the increase in absorbance also at 560 nm where the spectral differences between the substrate and the product complexes are maximum. The conventional mixing technique was followed and pseudo-first order conditions were employed throughout.

The plots of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ or $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$, (where A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances at time t and after completion of the reaction) against time were found to be non-linear, being curved at the initial stage but subsequently of constant slope (Fig. 3). The method of Weyh and Hamm¹⁹

was adopted to calculate rate constants for the two consecutive steps. We took the help of Origin 6.0 for other calculations. From the linear second portion, $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained from the plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time. Rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Fig. 3. Typical plot of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus time. $[\text{Complex}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{thiourea}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; pH = 7.4, Temp. = $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Results and discussion

The first acid dissociation equilibrium of the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ is 6.6^{20} at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At pH 7.4, the complex ion exists in a dimeric oxo-bridged form, $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ ^{21–25}. At pH 7.4, oxo-bridge structure of the title complex has already been described in our previous paper²⁶. A variable temperatures study does not show any effect, which is in line with the fact that the oxo-bridge formation is solely pH-dependent^{27,28}.

The pK_a value of thiourea is 2.0 at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ²⁹, so that at pH 7.4 it exists in the neutral form. On the other hand the pK_1 , pK_2 and pK_3 values of L-cysteine are 1.71, 8.33, 10.78 respectively at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ³⁰, which refer to the following dissociation process :

So at pH 7.4, the ligand L-cysteine exists as zwitterionic form, $\text{HS-CH}_2\text{-CH}(\text{NH}_3)^+\text{COO}^-$.

At constant temperature, pH, and fixed concentration of complex (1), the $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ or $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time plots for different ligand concentrations indicate that the substitution process involves a two-step consecutive process; the first step is dependent on ligand concentration, whereas the second step is independent of ligand concentration.

The rate constant for such a process can be evaluated by assuming Scheme 1, where A is the oxo-bridged diaqua complex, B is the intermediate with ligand, and C(2/3) is the final chelate product complex $[(\text{tap})_2\text{Ru}(\mu\text{-O})(\mu\text{-L})\text{Ru}(\text{tap})_2]^{2+}$.

Scheme 1

Calculation of k_1 for the $A \rightarrow B$ step :

The rate constant $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ for the $A \rightarrow B$ step can be evaluated by the method of Weyh and Hamm using the usual consecutive rate law which has already been described in our previous paper²⁶.

The values of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ were derived from the slopes of the $\ln \Delta$ versus time curves (where t is small) (Fig. 4). A similar procedure was applied for each ligand concentration in the $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ range, at constant $[(1)] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 7.4$, and at different temperatures namely 50, 55, 60 and 65 °C. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values are collected in Table 1.

The rate increases with an increase in ligand concentration and reaches to a limiting value (Fig. 5). Due to formation of outer-sphere association complex, limiting

Fig. 4. A typical plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time. $[\text{Complex}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{thiourea}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $\text{pH} = 7.4$, $\text{Temp.} = 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 5. Plots of $k_{1(\text{obs})} (\text{s}^{-1})$ versus $[\text{thiourea}]$ at different temperature, A = 50, B = 55, C = 60 and D = 65 °C.

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})} (\text{s}^{-1})$ values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures

$[\text{Complex}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 7.4$, ionic strength = $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$

Ligand	10^3 [ligand] (mol dm^{-3})	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)			
		50	55	60	65
Thiourea	1	1.40(0.01)	1.71(0.02)	2.38(0.01)	2.84(0.02)
	2	2.48(0.01)	2.94(0.01)	4.00(0.04)	4.79(0.02)
	3	3.35(0.02)	3.90(0.03)	5.08(0.02)	6.01(0.03)
	4	3.83(0.04)	4.55(0.03)	5.81(0.01)	6.71(0.01)
	5	4.27(0.01)	5.06(0.04)	6.28(0.03)	6.97(0.03)
L-Cysteine	1	0.75(0.02)	1.01(0.01)	1.23(0.01)	1.55(0.04)
	2	1.39(0.01)	1.92(0.02)	2.40(0.01)	2.79(0.02)
	3	1.94(0.04)	2.47(0.01)	3.05(0.02)	3.95(0.01)
	4	2.20(0.02)	2.93(0.03)	3.42(0.04)	4.22(0.03)
	5	2.54(0.02)	3.25(0.02)	3.84(0.01)	4.50(0.03)

rate is reached and the complex is stabilised by H-bonding. As the metal ion reacts with its immediate environment, a further change in ligand concentration beyond the saturation point will not affect the reaction rate. Based on the experimental findings, Scheme 2 may be proposed for the path A→B.

(where L = thiourea or L-cysteine)

Scheme 2

Based on Scheme 2, a rate expression can be derived :

$$d[\text{B}]/dt = k_1 K_E [\text{A}][\text{L}]$$

$$\text{or, } d[\text{B}]/dt = k_1 K_E [\text{L}] / (1 + K_E [\text{L}]) \cdot [\text{A}]_T$$

$$\text{We can write, } d[\text{B}]/dt = k_{1(\text{obs})} [\text{A}]_T$$

where subscript T stands for total concentration of Ru^{II} , i.e.

$$[\text{Ru}]_T = [\text{Ru}] (\text{free}) + [\text{Ru}\cdot\text{L}] (\text{outer-sphere associated})$$

Thus it can be written as

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1 K_E [\text{L}] / (1 + K_E [\text{L}]) \quad (1)$$

where k_1 is the rate constant for the A→B step; that is, the rate constant for the interchange of outer-sphere complex to the inner-sphere complex. K_E is the outer-sphere association equilibrium constant.

Equation can be represented as :

$$1/k_{1(\text{obs})} = 1/k_1 + 1/k_1 K_E [\text{L}] \quad (2)$$

The plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ against $1/[\text{L}]$ should be linear with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope $1/k_1 K_E$. This was found to be the case at all temperatures studied. The k_1 and K_E values were calculated from the intercept and slope (Fig. 6) and are collected in Table 2. From the temperature dependences of the K_E values thermodynamic parameters were calculated (Fig. 7).

Calculation of k_2 for B→C :

At a particular temperature, the slopes of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ or $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time plots at different ligand concentrations were found to be constant in the region where the plot is linear (Fig. 3). For different temperatures, the k_2 values are obtained directly from the limiting slopes and are collected in Table 3.

Fig. 6. Plots of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s) against $1/[\text{thiourea}]$, A = 50, B = 55, C = 60 and D = 65 °C.

Table 2. $10^3 k_1$ (s^{-1}) and K_E values for different ligands at different temperatures

[Complex] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , pH = 7.4 and ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO₄

Ligand	Temp. (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s^{-1})	K_E ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
Thiourea	50	9.38(0.007)	176
	55	10.18(0.002)	202
	60	11.12(0.003)	273
	65	12.13(0.006)	309
L-Cysteine	50	6.94(0.019)	122
	55	8.24(0.020)	141
	60	9.42(0.025)	153
	65	10.53(0.018)	174

Fig. 7. Plot of $\ln K_E$ versus $1/T$ for thiourea interactions with complex 1.

Table 3. $10^5 k_2$ (s^{-1}) values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , pH = 7.4, and ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO₄

Ligand	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)			
	50	55	60	65
Thiourea	14.17(0.03)	17.28(0.02)	20.58(0.01)	23.80(0.06)
L-Cysteine	2.86(0.003)	3.45(0.04)	4.19(0.03)	5.32(0.06)

*As the second step is independent of [Ligand], the values reported here is average value of all the data for different ligand concentrations at a particular temperature.

Effect of pH on the reaction rate :

The reactions were studied at five different pHs values. The k_{obs} values are found to increase with increase in pH in the studied pH range. The k_{obs} values are collected in Table 4. In the studied pH range (pH 5.5 to 7.4) with increase in pH the percentage of diaqua species of the

Table 4. The $10^3 k_{1(obs)}$ and $10^5 k_{2(obs)}$ values at different pHs

[Complex] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , [ligand] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 60 $^{\circ}C$, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO₄

Ligand	pH	$10^3 k_{1(obs)}$ (s^{-1})	$10^4 k_{2(obs)}$ (s^{-1})
Thiourea	5.5	2.70(0.03)	15.09(0.01)
	6.0	2.91(0.03)	15.70(0.04)
	6.5	3.27(0.01)	16.25(0.03)
	7.0	3.81(0.02)	17.02(0.01)
	7.4	4.00(0.04)	20.58(0.01)
L-Cysteine	5.5	1.76(0.04)	2.01(0.03)
	6.0	1.89(0.02)	2.12(0.02)
	6.5	2.06(0.04)	2.68(0.01)
	7.0	2.21(0.02)	3.57(0.03)
	7.4	2.40(0.01)	4.19(0.03)

complex is reduced and the percentage of the dimer is increased, and the dimer having two metal centers may be more acceptable to the incoming ligand. On the other hand with increase in pH the percentage of more reactive

A plausible mechanism is shown as below :

Fig. 8. Proposed mechanism for the interaction of thiourea with complex 1.

Fig. 9. Proposed mechanism for the interaction of L-cysteine with complex 1.

deprotonated ligand species increases which accounts for the increase in rate with increasing pH. We did not add any buffer in the kinetic solutions to maintain pH, because the buffer components may act as ligands.

Effect of temperature on the reaction rate :

Both the systems were studied at four different temperatures for different ligand concentrations and the anation rate constants for both $\text{A} \rightarrow \text{B}$ (k_1) and ring closure for $\text{B} \rightarrow \text{C}$ (k_2) steps are given in Tables 2 and 3. The activation parameters calculated from Eyring plots (Figs. S5 and S6) are given in Table 5. The procedure applied for this process is described in an earlier paper²⁶.

Mechanisms and conclusion

Our results indicate that the first step, i.e. the attack by the incoming ligand (both for thiourea and L-cysteine)

Table 5. Activation parameters for substitution of [complex 1] by ligands in aqueous medium, pH = 7.4

Ligands	ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_1^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_2^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Thiourea	12.45 ± 0.55	-246 ± 1.66	27.97 ± 0.63	-232 ± 1.92
L-Cysteine	21.86 ± 1.08	-219 ± 3.25	33.45 ± 2.77	-229 ± 8.39

proceeds by an associative interchange (Ia) mechanism. This proposition is supported by the following observations. First, with an increase in ligand concentration, saturation in the rate is observed. This indicates that an outersphere association complex is formed. Second, the low enthalpy of activation and large negative value of entropy of activation strongly suggest that the ligand participates in the transition state.

From the IR data of both thiourea substituted product

(2) and L-cysteine substituted product (3), it is clear that the S atom of both the ligands are participating in bonding. The S atom of C=S group of thiourea and S atom of -SH group of L-cysteine are involved in bonding with metal. This is consistent with the soft nature of both sulphur and ruthenium(II). Both thiourea and L-cysteine act as bridging ligand and in both the cases four membered rings are formed with the complex 1.

In the first step a rapid equilibrium is established, giving an outer-sphere complex between complex 1 and the ligands. The second step is the intramolecular ring closure which is independent on the incoming ligand concentration. Hence, the rate constant (k_2) for this step is also independent of ligand concentration.

The activation parameters for the first and second steps suggest an associative mode of activation for the substitution processes. From the temperature dependence of the K_E values the thermodynamic parameters are calculated $\Delta H^\circ = 35.25 \pm 3.74 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\circ = 152.07 \pm 11.47 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for thiourea), $\Delta H^\circ = 20.21 \pm 1.66 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\circ = 102.66 \pm 5.12 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for L-cysteine). The ΔG° values, calculated at all temperatures studied, have a negative magnitude which is once again in favour of the spontaneous formation of an outer-sphere association complex.

The rate of reaction also depends on steric effect. In case of L-cysteine the steric effect is more than thiourea which is reflected on the rate constant values (k_1 and k_2).

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